

The Influence of Alkali Cations on the Performance of Pt Electrodes in Kolbe Electrolysis of Acetic Acid

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Electrochemical decarboxylation of carboxylic acids is considered a sustainable method to improve the quality of pyrolysis oil. In this study, we assess the effect of monovalent alkali cations (of the acetates) on the performance of Pt electrodes in acid decarboxylation and the competing OER, using various electrochemical methods. We reveal a strong cation dependence generally following the trend $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ \sim \text{Cs}^+$ within a large pH range. Using rotating ring disc electrode measurements, we highlight the strong contribution of the oxygen evolution reaction particularly for electrolytes containing Li^+ and Na^+ which decreases the selectivity for Kolbe oxidation. In

addition, the faradaic efficiency (FE) towards methanol ranges between 16% (for Li^+) and 29% (for Cs^+) at high solution pH (9 or 12). The observed trends are generally explained by a cation-dependent interfacial pH and surface coverage of acetate, both lowest for Li. This is evident from differences in charge transfer resistance determined by impedance measurements and local pH measurements. Additionally, enhanced dissolution of Pt by Li^+ is also proposed. This work highlights that K^+ and Cs^+ cations favor FE for electrochemical Kolbe oxidation, at relatively low current densities.

Introduction

Deoxygenation of pyrolysis oil, a product of the pyrolysis of biomass (wood), is essential to allow further processing in refineries and to create environmentally more sustainable transportation fuels. Presently, deoxygenation is achieved by catalytic hydrogenation (hydrodeoxygenation – HDO), at elevated pressures and temperatures of 250–450 °C and 1–300 bar.^[1] Electrochemical deoxygenation of pyrolysis oil is potentially an alternative, environmentally more sustainable process. This includes both, the hydrogenation of oxygenates (aldehydes/ketones), as well as oxidative decarboxylation of acids, either through the Kolbe or Hofer Moest reactions.^[2–6] Electrochemical decarboxylation has other applications in commodity and speciality chemicals production.^[7–9] The anodic Kolbe or Hofer Moest reactions of carboxylic acids involve a series of proton-coupled electron transfer steps, including deprotonation, decarboxylation, disproportion, dimerization and esterification.^[4,10–12] The effectiveness and selectivity (Faradaic Efficiency) of electrodes in carboxylic acid oxidation depends on several process parameters, such as pH,^[13,14]

electrolyte composition,^[15,16] electrode material,^[17–20] and current density/applied voltage.^[21]

Generally, Kolbe electrolysis has been well investigated, however, the impact of the composition of alkali metal cations on the reaction has not been explored in detail. Early studies suggest that monovalent alkali metal cations do not significantly affect Kolbe electrolysis. Another study shows that multivalent cations negatively impact the Kolbe reaction.^[22]

Interestingly, monovalent alkali metal cations have been reported to affect several other electrode processes and their efficiency. For example, an influence of alkali metal cations was revealed for hydrogen peroxide formation^[23] and oxidation of methanol,^[24,25] glycerol,^[26] ethanol,^[27] urea,^[28] 1-heptanol,^[29] ethylene glycol,^[30] and formic acid,^[31] and the oxygen evolution reaction.^[32–35] These studies imply that an effect of the cation on carboxylic acid decarboxylation can be expected.

Theories attempting to describe the influence of cations in electrocatalytic reactions are numerous and include cation-dependent non-covalent interactions with adsorbed species on the electrode surface (see illustration in Scheme 1).^[36] The size of the hydrated cation is shown along with interaction either with surface OH^- (blue) or, relevant for the present study, acetate (brown). A non-covalent interaction of hydrated alkali metal (AM^+) cations during the oxygen evolution reaction (OER)^[33] has been suggested to occur via hydrogen bonding between hydrated non-specifically adsorbed cations and surface adsorbed OH_{ad} of the form $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{x-1} \text{AM}^+ \cdots \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdots \text{OH}_{\text{ad}}$ for larger monovalent cations such as K^+ and Cs^+ (indicated by the horizontal – multiple dashed lines) or a direct ion-dipole interaction between the non-specifically adsorbed cation and adsorbed OH_{ad} , i.e. $\text{OH}_{\text{ad}} \cdots \text{AM}^+(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ for the smaller partially ionized cations Li^+ and Na^+ (indicated by the presence of fewer dashed lines). Following the same analogy it is speculated that the nature of interactions, depending on the composition of

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Scheme 1. Schematic view of non-covalent interactions between the surface oxygenates and anions with the cations in the vicinity of the electrode.

the hydrated alkali metal cation, occurs via acetate instead of OH_{ad} for acetate decarboxylation (in Scheme 1).

To provide further clarification, as illustrated schematically, non-covalent interactions occur between molecules or parts of molecules without the involvement of a covalent bond. These interactions arise from various forces such as hydrogen bonding, cation-water interactions, cation-oxygenate and cation-hydroxide interactions.^[32] These interactions are characterised by relatively low stabilisation energies, typically in the order of less than 85 kJ/mol and have been suggested to significantly influence electro-oxidation reactions. For example for the OER reaction, Strmcnik et al.^[25] propose that cations with higher hydration energy ($\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$) interact more strongly with surface-adsorbed species (OH_{ad}) and thus affect the reaction rate.

It is worthwhile to mention that besides the differences in interactions shown in Scheme 1, monovalent cations might have additional effects on electrode performance (activity, selectivity, and stability), such as i) blocking of catalytic sites,^[37] ii) introduction of cation-induced changes of the interfacial pH,^[38] iii) a potential drop in the double layer region,^[39] iv) cations overcrowding the double layer,^[34] and v) alternation of the structure of the interfacial water layer.^[37]

For the OER, a significant effect was also reported for low concentrations of bivalent and trivalent cations, such as Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{2+} and Ca^{2+} , for a variety of electrodes.^[40–45]

Bivalent cations strongly impact the OER reaction and DFT calculations^[46] have shown that strong binding of cations with the (OER) reaction intermediates negatively impacts the activity. Similarly, multivalent cations negatively impact the Kolbe reaction.^[22] Thus, the local conditions at the electrode surface are also found to be determining factors for OER as evidenced by mechanistic calculations.^[34]

Based on the above, it can be hypothesized that cations should influence the electronic or structural properties of Pt oxides, the phase present under reaction conditions,^[47,48] affecting the kinetics (current density, FE, and selectivity) of acid decarboxylation, similar to observations made in the context of the OER. Moreover, prior research has shown that adsorption of alkali metal cations on the Pt surface affects the formation of its oxides.^[25] Platinum oxide formation is considered a prerequisite for Kolbe electrolysis allowing for stronger acetate radical binding further supporting the hypothesis that monovalent cations are indeed modulating Kolbe electrolysis.^[12,48]

In this study, we conducted a comprehensive experimental investigation to reveal the impact of cation composition on the OER, Kolbe, and Hofer Moest processes, across a wide range of (bulk) electrolyte pH (3–12) and applied current densities (10–50 mA/cm²). We employed online product detection and rotating ring-disk electrode (RRDE) measurements to reveal the product selectivity, and to measure the transition between oxygen evolution and Kolbe oxidation or Hofer Moest reaction, i.e., the inflection zone. The experimentally observed trends are tentatively explained by discussing interfacial interactions of the alkali cations with surface adsorbates, such as acetate – as illustrated in Scheme 1. Furthermore, acidification in the vicinity of the electrode surface, is expected to be more dominant for Li^+ and Na^+ -containing electrolytes, promoting OER compared to Kolbe product formation. Finally, we reveal the limitations of the cation effect and highlight that product selectivity is primarily affected at low production rates.

Results and Discussion

The iR-drop corrected cyclic voltammetry data obtained in the different acetate electrolytes (Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ or Cs^+) are summarized in Figure 1. At pH 3 the nature of the cation affects the slope of the i-V curve and the current density. For example, at 2.8 V_{RHE} clearly an increasing trend in current density in the order of $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ \sim \text{Cs}^+$ (Figure 1a) is observed. Upon increasing the electrolyte pH to pH 5, a similar trend is observed, particularly at applied potentials > 2.5 V_{RHE} where Kolbe electrolysis likely occurs. Besides this difference, the current onset potential (~ 1.8 V_{RHE}) is not affected by monovalent cations. At pH 9, and particularly at pH 12, a complex CV is obtained and the effect of the cation is depending on the applied potential. In the inflection zone (at ~ 2.5 V_{RHE} at pH 9 and at ~ 2.3 V_{RHE} at pH 12), in the presence of Li-acetate the highest current density is observed, while in the potential range in which presumably Kolbe oxidation occurs (at ~ 3 V_{RHE}), for Li^+ (and Na^+ at pH 9) acetate the lowest currents are obtained (Figures 2c and 2d). This can be rationalized by the complicated

Figure 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate oxidation using different cations (Li, Na, K and Cs). CVs were obtained at a scan speed of 100 mV/s in the potential range from 0–3 VRHE using a platinum working electrode. The electrolyte pH was adjusted to (a) pH 3 (b) pH 5 (c) pH 9 and (d) pH 12, respectively.

Figure 2. Faradaic efficiency to methane, ethylene, oxygen, ethane, and methanol determined by chronopotentiometric measurement in the batch cell setup with platinum anode. The reactor is coupled with inline gas chromatography and the reaction conditions are (a) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate pH 3 at 25 mA/cm² (b) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate pH 5 and 25 mA/cm² (c) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate pH 9 and 25 mA/cm² (d) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate pH 12 and 25 mA/cm². Note that to the residence time of the reactor is responsible for the low faradaic efficiency initially observed in the product time profiles (see Figure S6b, S12–14). The error bars represent the standard deviations of measurements from three repetitions conducted under identical conditions.

interaction of the various anions (OH_{ad}, CH₃COO_{ad} and CO₃²⁻) in the inner Helmholtz plane with the cations in the outer Helmholtz plane and in the bulk electrolyte.^[35] Furthermore, the inhibition of PtO formation may be advantageous for OER, which induce a low coverage of acetate when the electrode surface is in the metallic state.^[47]

In the presence of different monovalent cations a correlation was proposed between the (peak) current density and the cation hydration energy for OER.^[33] Such linear correlation can also be established in our study in acidic conditions, using the data of Figure 1 for OER (Figure S4). At higher electrolyte pH, i.e. pH > 9, such correlation is absent, due to the different order in cation effect on oxygen evolution. This suggests that the

cation hydration energy is less important in basic conditions – and the adsorption of acetate on the Pt surface interferes with the oxygen evolution reaction – in agreement with the absence of formation of O₂ in the backward scan – when the surface is likely in contact with high quantities of acetate. Moreover, concentration-dependent measurements performed with 0.63 M AM⁺ acetate and 1 M AM⁺ acetate electrolytes (Figure S5) confirm that cation-induced phenomena are related to surface adsorbed acetate.

Contrasting the work related to the influence of monovalent cations in OER, Kolbe electrolysis in the presence of different cations requires a detailed understanding of the product selectivity. Here, the product selectivity is expressed as Faradaic efficiency that has been determined as an average over the duration of the experiment (Figure 2, see supporting information for the full product distribution-time profiles). Measurements were performed at 25 mA/cm² to enable reproducible product detection of gas and liquid phase products. Although the cell did not contain a membrane, cross over and conversion of products formed at each electrode can be excluded on the basis of the observed 100% FE for most of the experiments. At low pH (Figure 2a and S6) oxygen is the only gas phase product detectable. The average FE for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) increases in the order of Li⁺ < Na⁺ < Cs⁺ ~ K⁺ with FE values ranging from 70–89% reflecting the trends observed in cyclic voltammetry. It is worthwhile to point out that the oscillation frequency of the potential (Figure S7) during the constant current experiments resembles earlier work,^[30] where the frequency pattern was assigned to variations in non-covalent interactions. During electrolysis, only minor differences in the FE (Figure S6b) are observed for K⁺ and Cs⁺ containing electrolytes and repetition of the experiments confirmed the cation dependency. Oxygen evolution is further supported by RRDE measurements (Figure S8), revealing that the efficiency towards OER as expressed by the ORR ring current is lower (–0.056 mA) in the presence of lithium acetate, compared to potassium acetate electrolytes (–0.14 mA). Independently of the cation, the low concentration of deprotonated acid (~17 mM) limits Kolbe electrolysis (Figure S6b). Still small quantities of CO₂ (FE~2–4%), a product of the Kolbe electrolysis, are detected suggesting that decarboxylation occurs at a low rate (Figure S9). Interestingly, for Li-based electrolytes the detectable amount of CO₂ is lowest and primarily for caesium-containing electrolytes a clear contribution of CO₂ evolution is noticeable, suggesting that acetate decarboxylation is favoured in these conditions. The deviation of the FE from unity might generally be explained by dissolution of Pt governed by the relatively high resistivity of the applied electrolytes and the resulting high applied potentials at the working electrode (Figure S6a).^[49,50]

Kolbe electrolysis to the coupling product ethane is considered to be favoured at an electrolyte pH close to the pK_a value (4.76) of acetic acid.^[13] Indeed at pH 5, a high averaged faradaic efficiency (above 82%) towards the coupling product ethane is observed for all cations, with the FE in case of potassium reaching close to 100%. The shift in FE towards ethane at pH 5 is caused by the coverage of the oxidized Pt

surface by an acetate layer,^[12,21] which requires a moderate concentration of deprotonated acid, also revealed by the clearly visible inflection zone in the CVs (Figure 1b). OER was found to be negligible for K^+ , while minor quantities of O_2 were detected for the other cations ($Cs^+ < Na^+ < Li^+$ as shown in Figure S12) – consequently lowering the FE of ethane in the inverse order following $Li^+ < Na^+ < Cs^+ < K^+$ (Figure 2b). Based on the above assessment, it is clear that Li^+ and Na^+ cations may induce significant dissolution of Pt at pH 3, and favourable oxygen evolution at pH 5 (minor quantities, see Figure S12), both assigned to similar surface and interfacial phenomena associated with the extent of the formation of Pt oxides^[48] and the coverage of the surface with acetate, respectively (see for an illustration Scheme 1).

Products associated with Hofer Moest reactions are observed for alkaline electrolytes of pH 9 and 12 (Figure 2c and 2d; for additional information see also Figure S13–S14 in the SI). As previously reported, dissolution of CO_2 (as indicated by the low FE towards CO_2 depicted in Figure S9), in the alkaline electrolyte causes formation of carbonate and a shift in reaction selectivity from Kolbe to Hofer Moest products.^[13] The averaged FE towards ethane, ranging from 59% to 70%, varies again in the order of $Li^+ < Na^+ < Cs^+ < K^+$, while the FE towards methanol ranges from 16% (for Li^+) to 29% (for Cs^+). Thus contrasting ethane formation, methanol formation is slightly favoured for a Cs^+ over a K^+ containing electrolyte at pH 9. At pH 12 (Figure 2d), the product selectivity further shifts towards Hofer Moest products, with the highest FE for methanol again observed in the presence of Cs^+ cations. Interestingly, cyclic voltammetry performed after electrolysis (see Figure S15) did not provide indications for higher concentrations of methanol: contrary, for K^+/Cs^+ acetate containing electrolytes a lower current density in the relevant potential region of oxidation of methanol, compared to Li^+ or Na^+ containing electrolyte, is observed. Likely a higher acetate coverage of the Pt electrode surface in the presence of Cs^+/K^+ inhibits methanol oxidation, as previously already reported for ethanol electrooxidation.^[51] A shift in the methanol oxidation onset would imply that for Li^+/Na^+ -containing electrolytes a stronger decrease in pH occurs. Nevertheless, Kolbe activity is consistently increasing in the order of Li^+ (46%) $< Na^+ < Cs^+ < K^+$ (61%). Similar to the measurements performed at lower pH, for alkaline conditions the electron-balance is not closed for lithium and sodium-containing electrolytes, likely related to platinum dissolution. Since platinum dissolution was reported to be dependent on the nature of the cation (alkali and triethylamine),^[52] the formation of soluble complexes might be favoured in the presence of lithium cations. We will now continue by confirming the differences between cations in the OER and acetate decarboxylation reactions, followed by an assessment of the interfacial pH.

Confirmation of the Changing FE From O_2 to Acetate Decarboxylation in the Inflection Zone

RRDE measurements were performed at optimized conditions (pH 5). The transition between OER and the Kolbe reaction is reflected by an inflection zone, as described by Chan et al.^[12] using microkinetic modeling and DFT calculations. Using the measurement protocol shown in Figure 3a in which cyclic voltammetry is performed at the Pt disk, while a potentiostatic measurement at the ring allows for in situ oxygen detection, it is confirmed that the inflection zone indeed describes the transition from OER to Kolbe reaction. This is even more

Figure 3. RRDE measurement for estimating the inflection zone where OER ceases to compete with the Kolbe reaction. (a) Schematic diagram of the RRDE setup used for acetic acid decarboxylation, including the Pt disk and Pt ring to detect O_2 by the current induced by the ORR. (b) CV scans from 0.5–3 V_{RHE} of 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate (pH 5) at 1500 rpm at 100 mV/s with simultaneous observation of ORR currents on the ring electrode (c) CV representation of the acetic acid/ Cs^+ -acetate coverage and illustration of the inflection zone. The peak at 2.5–2.6 V_{RHE} shows the transition of the OER to the Kolbe reaction at 1 mV/s.

apparent for CVs performed at a low scan rate (Figure 3c). The selectivity changes from OER to Kolbe at approx. $2.5 V_{RHE}$ (Figure 3b and c).

In the presence of Cs^+ cations (Figure 3c), the ring current is initially increasing exponentially. From approx. $2.1 V_{RHE}$ to $2.3 V_{RHE}$, a steady ring current is observed before the ORR current on the ring decreases and completely fades at a disk potential of $3 V_{RHE}$. Considering the close to unity Faradaic efficiency determined by the product gas analysis (Figure 2), inhibition of OER is clearly a prerequisite for Kolbe electrolysis.^[11–13]

The suppression of the OER for K^+ and Cs^+ is in strong contrast with the ORR currents observed for Li^+ and Na^+ -containing electrolytes. Particularly in the presence of Li^+ cations, an exponential increase in ORR current is observed, before at $2.4 V_{RHE}$ the ring current induced by ORR remains constant. Interestingly, the ring current even starts to increase again at disk potentials $>2.8 V_{RHE}$, probably related to a decrease in local surface pH favouring the OER reaction. The RRDE measurements further highlight the significance of the nature of the cations on the OER and Kolbe reaction and align with the other measurements in the sense that at potentials above the inflection zone, suppression of the OER is cation dependent following the order $Li^+ < Na^+ < Cs^+ < K^+$.

Determination of the Local pH

The near-surface pH during Kolbe electrolysis (1 M acetic acid/ AM^+ -acetate, pH 5 at $25 mA/cm^2$) was determined using a pH meter with a sensing tip surrounded by a plastic body and a side opening placed near the Pt electrode surface (1.8 mm distance).

A decrease in pH was observed for all cations used with the extent of pH decrease following the order Li^+ (pH 3.1) $<$ Na^+ (pH 4.2) $<$ K^+ (pH 4.4) $<$ Cs^+ (pH 4.5) as illustrated in Figure 4a and Figure S16. The changes in pH were further analysed using RRDE measurements, allowing to deduce pH changes even closer to the electrode surface using the pH-dependency of the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) as sensing tool.^[53] RRDE measurements were performed without rotation using the two cations that showed the most prominent difference, i.e. the cation considered to enable the highest (K^+) and lowest (Li^+) activity for Kolbe electrolysis. The CV scans obtained at the disk electrode (Figure 4b) reveal a shift in hydrogen evolution to more positive potentials in the presence of the lithium-containing acetate compared to measurements with potassium acetate. This is indicative of a lower pH during electrolysis in Li^+ -electrolytes.^[53–55] The determined pH-dependence aligns well with the RRDE and Faradaic efficiency measurements, where higher ORR currents in the presence of lithium cations at high potentials (see Figure 3b) and exclusive oxygen evolution for measurements performed at pH 3 (Figure 2) were observed. Thus, the local pH during electrolysis should be considered to fully describe the influence of cations on the electrochemical activity of the Kolbe reaction.^[54]

Figure 4. (a) Probing the pH measurement near the electrode surface during Kolbe electrolysis at the pH measurement employing the pH meter during electro-oxidation of 1 M acetic acid/ AM^+ -acetate at pH 5 during constant current electrolysis on a platinum foil at $25 mA/cm^2$. (b) Shift in the hydrogen evolution by means of RRDE for the local pH change during Kolbe electrolysis. (c) Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy EIS of mixed OER and Kolbe reaction at pH 5 and (d) EIS measurement at pH 12.

Surface Coverage by Charge Transfer Resistances

The electrode reaction and interfacial phenomena in the presence of different cations is finally studied using potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (PEIS). For PEIS measurements the electrode is polarized at a sufficiently large potential to start decarboxylation i.e. the electrode is polarized at $2.1 V_{RHE}$.^[56,57] Due to extreme bubble evolution, higher potentials were not considered. PEIS measurements at pH 5 show that the solution resistance varies (to a minor extent) in the expected order of $Li^+ > Na^+ > K^+ > Cs^+$. The charge transfer resistance (see Table S2) extracted from the Nyquist plot (Figure 4c–d) is lowest in the presence of Li acetate (250.3Ω). With increasing surface coverage of anions (OH, acetate and carbonates), the charge transfer resistance increases due to an increased anion coverage/film thickness and a lower electro-active surface area. Since lithium is considered to form strong non-covalent bonds to oxygenates and acetate species (Scheme 1), the low charge transfer resistance is indicative of a low acetate coverage, confirmed by the RRDE and Faradaic efficiency measurements. The higher charge transfer resistance in the presence of K-cations aligns well with the high Faradaic efficiency towards Kolbe products due to the formation of a thicker acetate layer favoured by the weaker non-covalent interactions. In the transition regime of OER and Kolbe, for both Na^+ and Cs^+ electrolytes ethane and oxygen were detected explaining the minor differences in charge transfer resistance observed in PEIS measurements.

At pH 12 (Figure 4d), the determined charge transfer resistance is generally high compared to the resistances observed at pH 5 and varies considerably for the different cations. This is attributed to the high surface concentrations of hydroxyl ions, and the fast conversion of formed CO_2 to carbonates (see also Figure S17).^[13] The carbonate ions interfere

with the acetate layer, which leads to carbonium ion formation and subsequent alcohol instead of Kolbe product formation.^{[4][13]} The accumulation of ionic species and possible precipitation of salts on the Pt anode will lead to a higher charge transfer resistance as compared to the measurements performed at pH 5. Moreover a deviation in the consistently observed cation trend is observed. For electrolytes with pH > 9, the charge transfer resistance increases in the order of $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ \ll \text{Cs}^+$, which nevertheless correlates well with the favourable formation of methanol in Cs^+ -containing electrolyte.

Limitations of the Cation Effects

The surface structure and coverage of the Pt working electrode is of importance in Kolbe electrooxidation. We demonstrated that the precise surface coverage is highly dependent on the cation composition, affecting the local pH and surface coverage of acetate. Though the experimental observations agree well with the theory of cation induced non-covalent interactions (Scheme 1), it is important to note that also the oxidation of the Pt surface^[12,48,58] is affected by monovalent cations of smaller radii. These summarized phenomena are also affected by a factor we have not discussed previously, which is the applied current density.

At low current density (10 mA/cm²), the concentration of methyl radicals at the electrode surface is low and hence the probability of dimerization, and associated formation of ethane, is low. In the presence of different cations the probability of dimerization is in agreement with the established trend at 25 mA/cm² of $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Cs}^+ < \text{K}^+$ (Figure S19–S21), but with generally lower FEs to ethane. The lower applied electrode potential to obtain 10 mA/cm² results in a higher contribution of the OER, particularly for Li^+ , Na^+ and Cs^+ -containing electrolyte, confirming the arrangement of ions in the double-layer region and the concentration of active species at the electrode surface changes as a function of applied current density. In alkaline media and in the presence of Li-acetate (Figure 5b), we observe an increase in the FE to ethane with increasing current density, while in the presence of K^+ the product distribution is the same for measurements performed at 25 mA/cm² or 50 mA/cm². This again reveals that a PtO

surface fully covered with an acetate layer is easily obtained in the presence of potassium, in agreement with RRDE investigations. Comparing Li^+ and K^+ electrolytes using chronopotentiometric measurements performed at 50 mA/cm², the product distribution is essentially the same, and the cation effect is thus not observable. Following our investigations, it will be intriguing to explore the effect of cations under other conditions, considering the Kolbe reaction is also affected by temperature (conversion effects have been reported for temperatures < 10 °C and above > 50 °C^[59]) and the nature of carboxylic acid (different chain lengths and mixtures of acids). Particularly, the interaction of cations with longer chain acids will enrich the understanding of Kolbe electrolysis for many applications.

Conclusions

In this work, we studied the electrochemical oxidation of acetic acid (Kolbe electrolysis) using Pt electrodes, and explored the influence of monovalent alkali metal cations (Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ and Cs^+) on the product distribution and overall electrochemical activity. Potassium cations are shown to be most suitable for Kolbe electrolysis at pH 5. At low current densities (25 mA/cm²), a trend in activity and selectivity, $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Cs}^+ < \text{K}^+$, was observed throughout the entire pH range, i.e. at pH 3 where OER is dominating, pH 5 where OER transitioned to Kolbe electrolysis and pH 9 where Hofer Moest reaction occur, predominantly in the presence of Cs^+ cations. With increasing current densities (> 50 mA/cm²), the influence of the cation on the electro-oxidation decreases. Moreover, using RRDE measurements we confirmed that the OER is entirely suppressed in the presence of K^+ cations at potentials of $\sim 2.5 V_{\text{RHE}}$ (inflection zone), while for Li^+ OER still proceeds. A change in transfer resistance and local pH with larger cations due to the formation of a thick acetate layer, which inhibits OER, is also in agreement with the observed electrochemical behavior. The local pH decrease is particularly pronounced in presence of Li^+ cations. Consequently OER is favored even at a bulk pH of 5. In conclusion, this study reveals the significance of alkali monovalent cations in the electrochemical decarboxylation of carboxylic acids.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.

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Figure 5. Faradaic efficiency to methane, ethylene, oxygen, ethane, and methanol during chrono-potentiometric measurements in the three electrode undivided batch cell setup coupled with inline gas chromatography (a) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺-acetate pH 5 at 10 mA/cm² (b) 1 M acetic acid/AM⁺ (Li/K)-acetate pH 12 at 10, 25 and 50 mA/cm². The error bars represent the standard deviations of measurements from three repetitions conducted under identical conditions.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: Kolbe electrolysis · monovalent alkali metal cations · hofer most reaction · non-covalent interaction · oxygen evolution reaction

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